

Dyes derived from Itaconic Acid.

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Itaconic acid resembles succinic acid in some physical and chemical properties, *e.g.*, in solubility and in formation of anhydride, acid chloride and imide. But from the point of view of molecular strain itaconic acid, which is methylene succinic acid, on account of its unsaturated linkage, contains a more strained system than succinic acid, and therefore it was expected that dyes derived from itaconic acid by condensation with various aromatic hydroxy and amino compounds would have more colour than the corresponding derivatives of succinic acid (*cf.* Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 1171). It has been found in practice that the condensation products of itaconic acid, which have been thus obtained, have a deeper colour than the corresponding succineins.

Itaconic acid condenses with aromatic hydroxy and amino compounds directly, but it has been found that the addition of a suitable condensing agent leads to a much better yield. Sulphuric acid and tin tetrachloride have been found to be the most suitable in this respect. The constitution of these compounds can be represented as follows, regarding the phenol- and resorcinol-itaconeins as typical members : —

Resorcinol itaconein.

Phenol-itaconein.

The following aromatic hydroxy and amino compounds have been condensed with itaconic acid and the corresponding itaconeins obtained :—phenol, resorcinol, catechol, phloroglucinol, pyrogallol and

m-diethylamido-phenol. The condensation product with resorcinol has been brominated and a hexa-bromo compound obtained. This bromo compound, which dissolves in dilute alkalis with a brilliant crimson colour, has been found by direct comparison to have a more intense colour, and stronger dyeing properties than ordinary eosin, which is tetrabromo-resorcinol-phthalein, and than tetra-bromo-resorcinol succinein. This greatly intensified colour development is probably due to the two extra bromine atoms.

The condensation product with catechol has been obtained in the form of a hydrochloride, which, from its chemical properties, seems to be an oxonium derivative. The hydrochloride is easily decomposed by water into hydrochloric acid and catechol-itaconein, but its tin chloride double salt seems to be stable and dissolves in water with an intense magenta colour.

In general properties, colour and fluorescence, it has been found that the dyes derived from itaconic acid are similar to the corresponding substances obtained from succinic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenol-itaconein.

A mixture of itaconic acid (5 g.) phenol (14.6 g.) and tin tetrachloride (25 g.) was heated on the water-bath under reflux for 16 hours. The product was poured into water and the excess of phenol distilled off in steam. The residue was then extracted with dilute ammonia and the extract, after filtration, was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid. The greyish white precipitate of the crude phenol-itaconein thus obtained was purified by dissolving in dilute ammonia and precipitating with dilute hydrochloric acid a number of times until it was almost white in appearance; m. p. 210°.

The substance is very soluble in the ordinary organic solvents and also in alkalis in which it dissolves with a brilliant pink colour. (Found: C, 72.01; H, 5.7. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.35; H, 4.9 per cent.).

Resorcinol-itaconein.

A mixture of itaconic acid (8.9 g.) and resorcinol (6.6 g.) was heated on the oil-bath at 130-140° for nearly 3 hours with the

addition of sulphuric acid (0.5 c.c.). The melt after cooling was dissolved in alcohol and treated with an alcoholic solution of lead acetate. The bright orange precipitate of the lead lake was filtered off, washed with alcohol and then decomposed with hydrogen sulphide in alcoholic suspension. The precipitated lead sulphide was removed and the alcoholic mother-liquor, on concentration to a small volume and cautious dilution with water, yielded the resorcinol-itaconeïn in the form of a bright yellow crystalline powder. By repetition of the above process a number of times the substance was obtained in a pure condition, m. p. 195° (decomp.).

The substance is very soluble in alcohol, acetone and acetic acid, but insoluble in ether, benzene, ligroïn and water. It dissolves in alkalis with a yellow colour, and the solution on dilution shows a brilliant green fluorescence. The solution in organic solvents also shows similar fluorescence. (Found : C, 68.69 ; H, 3.99. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4$ requires C, 68.9 ; H, 4.00 per cent.).

Catechol-itaconeïn (hydrochloride).

A mixture of itaconic acid (6 g.), catechol (10.15 g.) and tin tetrachloride (25 g.) was heated on the water-bath under reflux for 3 hours. The melt was then poured into water in which it dissolved completely forming a magnificent magenta coloured solution containing a tin chloride double salt. The solution was acidulated with dilute hydrochloric acid and treated with hydrogen sulphide until the tin was completely precipitated. The light pink coloured filtrate from the precipitated tin sulphide was concentrated to a small volume and kept in a desiccator containing quick lime and caustic potash for nearly a week when masses of colourless crystals appeared. These were filtered and dried in a vacuum desiccator ; m. p. 165° (decomp.).

The substance is extremely soluble in water and is highly hygroscopic. The colourless solution in water on treatment with dilute alkali develops a dirty pink colour which is discharged on the

addition of acid. It contains one molecule of hydrogen chloride and its chemical properties indicate that it is an oxonium derivative. (Found: C, 61.5; H, 3.6; Cl, 10.8. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2Cl$ requires C, 61.44; H, 3.9; Cl, 10.5 per cent.).

Phloroglucinol-itaconëin.

Phloroglucinol (9.7 g.) and itaconic acid (5 g.) were mixed and heated on an oil-bath at 130-140° for three hours with the addition of a few drops of sulphuric acid. The melt was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and after filtration was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was purified by solution in alkali and reprecipitation with dilute acid in the same manner a number of times until it was obtained in a crystalline condition; m. p. above 290° (decomp.).

It is a dark brown substance which is moderately soluble in organic solvents and very soluble in alkalis in which it dissolves with a blood-red colour. The solution is not fluorescent. (Found: C, 61.8; H, 3.8. $C_{17}H_{13}O_7$ requires C, 62.2; H, 3.6 per cent.).

Pyrogallol-itaconëin.

A mixture of itaconic acid (6 g.), pyrogallol (11.6 g.) and tin tetrachloride (25 g.) was heated on the water-bath under reflux for six hours. The melt was poured into water when a mauve coloured precipitate was obtained. It was dissolved in hot concentrated hydrochloric acid, the solution diluted with water and then the tin completely precipitated from solution by hydrogen sulphide. The filtrate from the tin sulphide was evaporated to a small volume and kept in a desiccator containing quick lime and caustic potash for nearly a week at the end of which the colouring matter separated in masses of black crystals. These were filtered off, washed with water and then dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The substance is slightly soluble in organic solvents and insoluble in water. It is very soluble in concentrated acids and also in

alkalis in which it dissolves with a dirty pink colour; m. p. 253° (decomp.). (Found: C, 62.3; H, 3.2; C₁₁H₁₁O₄, requires C, 62.9; H, 3.6 per cent.).

m-Diethylamidophenol-itaconeïn.

A mixture of itaconic acid (6 g.) and *m*-diethylamidophenol (15.2 g.) was heated on the oil-bath at 130-140° with a few drops of sulphuric acid for five hours. The cold melt was extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid and the filtered extract precipitated with dilute sodium carbonate. The tarry precipitate was dissolved in alcohol and the solution boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. From the filtrate the alcohol was distilled off and the residue dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and reprecipitated with sodium carbonate solution. The substance was thus obtained in dark pink crystals which were collected and dried in a vacuum desiccator; m. p. 80° (decomp.).

The substance is very soluble in organic solvents and in dilute acids with a bright pink colour and a deep brown fluorescence. (Found: N, 6.5. C₂₂H₂₀O₄N₂, requires N, 6.8 per cent.).

Tetrabromo-resorcinol-itaconeïn-dibromide.

Resorcinol-itaconeïn (1 mol.) was brominated in glacial acetic acid solution with excess of bromine (7 mol.) by heating on the water-bath under reflux for an hour. The solution was then poured into water and the blood-red precipitate of the eosin thus obtained collected and washed with water, and dried in the steam oven. The substance was thus obtained as fine crystalline powder, m. p. 187° (decomp.).

The substance is moderately soluble in organic solvents and very soluble in alkalis in which it dissolves with a brilliant violet red colour. The solution is not fluorescent. (Found : Br, 62.0, C₁₇, H₉O₄Br₂ requires Br, 62.1 per cent.).

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